
MTB-MLE Curriculum: An Evaluative Study on Language Transitioning Design for Basic Education

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ABSTRACT: The purpose of this phenomenological study was to elicit teachers' lived experiences of teaching Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education (MTB-MLE) in the primary grades. It sought to evaluate the MTB-MLE program in Dawis Elementary School in Digos City, Philippines particularly in its effects in the curriculum, instruction, and assessment, the effect of the transition from mother tongue to English language, and how teachers address the challenges they encountered in the implementation of MTB-MLE. In-depth interview (IDI) was conducted to the participants who handled learners from diverse tribes. Eight (8) significant themes emerged from the effects of MTB-MLE in terms of Curriculum, Instruction and Assessment divided into two categories: success and struggles. For the success: Easy Understanding of Concepts and Enhancement of Students' Engagement surfaced as themes. For the struggles: Linguistic Problems, Transition Challenges, Construction of non-standardized test, Inadequate Instructional Materials, Teacher Training Difficulty, and No Codified Dialects cropped up. Four (4) significant themes emerged in the transition from Mother Tongue to English Language to the learners: lexical problems, lack of instructional materials, translation difficulties, and comprehension difficulties. Five (5) themes in terms of the strategies that teachers address during the transition from Mother Tongue to English language appeared: Translation of target language to mother tongue, Utilization of Multilingual Resources, Utilization of technological aids, Use of scaffolding and bridging in instruction, and enhancing and optimizing the learning experience of students. The study's findings shed light for evaluating the MTB-MLE curriculum. School administrators may find this study to be helpful in providing insights for enhancing the MTB-MLE curriculum. Likewise, results of the study may provide incisive contributions to the ongoing discourse on MTB-MLE.

KEYWORDS: Climate Change, Figure of Speech, Persuasive Language, Environmental Speech

1. INTRODUCTION

The Philippines is the only nation in South East Asia with a national policy mandating Mother Tongue-based Multilingual Education (MTB-MLE) during the elementary school years (UNESCO, 2018). As a result, the rest of the region looks to the Philippines as a model for how to adopt MTB-MLE (Rola, 2017). However, this raises an argument on the intricate problem of language policy in education, which presents a difficult setting for putting into practice a language policy that will benefit the entire nation. For instance, teachers face many problems and difficulties when implementing the MTB-MLE Curriculum because of some issues on lack of references written in mother tongue, lack of teachers' training seminars, pupils' lack of interest in the mother tongue, lack of teachers teaching in the first language, and lack of teachers who can teach the students using the language of the locals or the community that he/she is assigned to (Hernandez & Duguiang, 2019).

The following are the problems and difficulties that the teachers encountered when putting MTB-MLE as language transitioning design for basic education into practice. One is the lack of references written in mother tongue; This is the situation where there are not enough resources available in the mother tongue, such as dictionaries, books, textbooks, and the like, to meet the demands of students with various mother tongues (Hernandez & Duguiang, 2019). Another is the, lack of teachers' trainings and seminars; Teachers that work with multilingual students need to be orientated and guided on how to deal with students who speak multiple languages. Therefore, training and seminars are crucial (UNESCO, 2018). In addition, pupils' lack of interest in the mother tongue; The teacher's observation of the students' lack of interest in their mother tongue represents another difficulty. Observably, kids have no interest in using it as their language of teaching, which makes it difficult for the teachers to hold their attention (Bautista, 2015). In addition, according to Bajas et. al., (2017), lack of teachers teaching in the first language; is another difficulty that neither teachers nor students are native speakers of the language in question, and pedagogical knowledge is not adequately acquired and utilized. As we all know, instructional materials provide or helps in instilling knowledge to the children. Without these, it is very difficult to teach (Hernandez & Duguiang, 2019). Lastly, lack of teachers who can teach the students using the language of the locals or the community that he/she is assigned to. This one falls under the second problem that I mentioned because this can be helped thru

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trainings and seminars. If only teachers are taught on how to handle this situation, it would be of great help to them to lessen their load in conducting classes (Gargeda & Lumabi, 2019).

In the blog post entitled "Mother Tongue Based Multilingual Education in the Philippines: Its Success and Struggle" by JD (2021), a national correspondent of MeridiE in the Philippines it is pointed out that a teacher from Davao City, Region XI (name undisclosed for confidentiality purposes) emphasizes the advantages of using Sinugbuanong Binisaya or Cebuano as a medium of instruction. The insights from this teacher shed light on the positive results of the MTB MLE program. By teaching in their regional language, teachers feel more comfortable when providing comprehensive explanations. Leading to a deeper understanding of the lessons for both educators and students. The teacher also highlights the importance of allowing students to connect with their native dialect enabling them to express their thoughts more effectively during classroom discussions. As a result. The implementation of MTB MLE has produced noteworthy improvements in students' reading levels (Mayol, 2017).

Furthermore, according to the teachers from the blog written by JD, a national correspondent of MeridiE in the Philippines it would be beneficial to reposition MTB-MLE as a separate subject instead of a teaching method. They would like to convey this recommendation to policymakers and experts at the Department of Education. They believe that by doing so, students would become more familiar with their regional dialect while still learning Filipino and English (Ramos, 2019). Additionally, according to Ramos (2019) the teachers urge policymakers and DepEd experts to conduct research on the long-term effects of using MTB-MLE as a teaching and learning strategy. Finally, the teachers suggest that policymakers and DepEd officials take these issues into careful consideration to enable them to better serve their responsibility to their students. They find it difficult to teach when training sessions, practices, and the necessary resources for efficient utilization of MTB-MLE are lacking (Mayol, 2017).

Teachers have found strategies to make up for the problems they have faced. Since the government did little to solve these flaws, teachers have been forced to rely on their own abilities to tailor their lessons in order to meet the needs of the students (Cruz, 2019). That being the case, by putting the teachers through training seminars to develop their teaching strategies, educators will be able to meet the needs of their students better and support their achievement in their academic performance, especially language learners. Moreover, by providing opportunities for practice and feedback where students need to practice using the language to develop their language skills. Teachers should provide opportunities for students to practice speaking, reading, writing, and listening in their mother tongue. Providing feedback on their language use can help students improve their mother tongue language skills (Kosonen & Hirotani, 2017).

The **Mother Tongue – Based Multilingual Education** is a form of multilingual education that emphasizes the use of the student's mother tongue as the first language of instruction before introducing other languages such as Filipino and English. According to Malone (2023) this approach aims to address the issue of functional illiteracy among Filipinos by allowing children to express themselves more freely and encouraging them to participate actively in the learning process. The implementation of MTB-MLE in the Philippines was the result of a prolonged process that included the development of theories, their validation, and evidence-based campaigning. The approach is grounded in the Education for All (EFA) framework, which seeks to implement integrative language and educational policies that ensure the sustainability of educational initiatives (Malone, 2023).

It is unclear whether the Department of Education (DepEd) in the Philippines is adequately prepared to implement the MTB MLE program. Teachers have used various strategies to compensate for the materials needed to effectively teach the program. However, there have been no studies conducted on the difficulties, adjustments, and measures taken by teachers at Dawis Elementary School in Digos City, Davao del Sur to teach MTB-MLE effectively. While many studies have focused on teachers in Luzon, there are few studies on this topic in Mindanao, particularly in Digos City. Also, by carrying out this study in our community, we can help our educational system by figuring out how to support local teachers while teaching Mother Tongue – Based Multilingual Education. As future teachers, this study is essential as it will give us a comprehensive understanding of the challenges that teachers face. This knowledge will better prepare us to address these challenges when we become teachers.

2. Research Objectives

This study will evaluate the MTB-MLE curriculum on language in Dawis Elementary School Digos City as transitioning design for basic education.

Specifically, it will answer the following questions:

1. What effect does the MTB-MLE program have in primary education in terms of the curriculum, instruction, and assessment in Dawis Elementary School, Digos City?
2. How does the transition from mother tongue to English language affect the learners?
3. In what ways do teachers address the challenges brought about by the transition from Mother Tongue to English language to the performance of the learners?

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3. Methodology

3.1 Research Participants

This study's participants were all first- to third-grade teachers, three teachers per grade level and have at least five months of experience in teaching. Most of the nine (9) teachers are from Cebuano tribe while one was Kalagan and another one was from an Ilonggo tribe. As shown in Table 1, these teachers handled varied students of diverse tribes – some were from Kalagan, Blaan, Mandaya, Manobo, and mostly from Cebuano or Bisaya tribes. This study was conducted in the Dawis Elementary School located at Dawis Purok Talakitok, Digos City it has three sections per level, as they are the ones who taught, guided, and developed the language abilities of their students utilizing the MTB-MLE program during the transition. The choice to focus on Dawis Elementary School for this study is motivated by its unique attributes and its diverse student population. The school provides education to students from different Lumad tribal groups in Mindanao – Bagobo, Kalagan, Manobo, Mandaya, and B'laan – who do not have Bisaya as their first language. This is particularly significant because Bisaya serves as the medium of instruction for the MTB-MLE Curriculum at Dawis Elementary School.

Table 1. PROFILE OF THE PARTICIPANTS

Grade Level	Participant	Years in teaching	Tribe of the Participant	Number of the learners in the class	Tribe of the Learners (ex. 10% of the learners are Blaan)
1	1	12	Cebuano	Male – 15 Female – 20 Total: 35	Blaan – 1 2.857% Kalagan – 7 20% Manobo – 1 2.857% Bisaya – 24 75%
	2	17	Cebuano	Male – 17 Female – 15 Total: 32	Kalagan – 8 25% Bisaya – 24 75%
	3	8 months	Cebuano	Male – 14 Female – 17 Total: 31	Bagobo – 1 3.226% Manobo – 1 3.226% Kalagan – 5 16.129% Blaan – 5 16.129% Bisaya – 18 61.129%
2	4	27	Cebuano	Male – 22 Female – 17 Total: 39	Kalagan – 5 12.821% Bisaya – 34 87.179%
	5	7	Kalagan	Male – 30 Female – 16 Total: 46	Kalagan – 8 17.391% Bagobo – 1 2.174% Bisaya – 37 80.435%
	6	17	Ilonggo	Male – 19 Female – 14 Total: 33	Kalagan – 2 6.061% Blaan – 1 3.03% Mandaya – 1 3.03% Bisaya – 30 87.879%
3	7	5	Cebuano	Male – 28 Female – 17 Total: 45	Kalagan – 4 8.89% Blaan – 2 4.444% Bisaya – 39 86.667%
	8	14	Cebuano	Male – 15 Female – 19 Total: 34	Kalagan – 3 8.824% Bisaya – 31 91.176%
	9	21	Cebuano	Male – 15 Female – 16 Total: 31	Kalagan – 3 18.75% Bisaya – 28 90.323%

The purpose of this study is to gain firsthand knowledge about the challenges faced by educators while working with learners who came from different tribal backgrounds and speak different first languages. Researchers anticipate that by exploring these teachers'

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perspectives and strategies they will reveal a range of challenges as well as instructional approaches and innovative methods for engaging and supporting students. This investigation holds the promise of advancing knowledge on these matters and providing valuable suggestions to enhance the implementation of the MTB MLE curriculum in classrooms with a variety of linguistic backgrounds.

This multi-tribal context creates an opportunity to explore how language and culture interact within an educational setting. Moreover, the geographic location of Dawis Elementary School, in a remote area near the bay, presents further complexities when it comes to language transition precisely because teachers must navigate linguistic and cultural differences.

Studying how teachers address student needs at Dawis Elementary School will offer insights into effective instructional strategies, cultural sensitivity, and inclusive education practices. The findings from this study will inform targeted interventions and best practices that can be applied to similar schools with diverse student populations.

Furthermore, opting for Dawis Elementary School as our research site provides us with an opportunity to analyze the complexities involved in language transition as well as unpacking the difficulties encountered by children originating from various tribal backgrounds. It is important to note that though this study might not capture every school's situation. Its findings will greatly enhance our knowledge on effective implementation strategies for the MTB MLE curriculum. Thus. These discoveries hold immense potential for influencing teaching practices and policies across diverse educational environments.

This study holds immense significance in the chosen area because it imparts vital knowledge and understanding to future teachers who will engage with students from various tribal backgrounds. It enables these teachers to develop a comprehensive comprehension of the difficulties encountered when transitioning between languages and offers valuable advice on adapting teaching techniques particularly when Bisaya is predominant. By acknowledging these issues and presenting practical solutions we can establish inclusive learning environments that facilitate academic progress for all students.

This school is a public-school offering KG 1- KG 2 and first six years of compulsory education (grades 1–6) informally divided into 3 years of primary level and 3 years of intermediate level. Creswell (2013) suggests that the information-gathering process typically involves conducting primary in-depth interviews with approximately ten individuals in a phenomenological research study. However, the necessary number of interviews may vary depending on the type of research and research question being investigated (Creswell & Creswell, 2018). Creswell 2013 suggest that ten individuals should be involved in conducting primary in-depth as participants in the study; hence the school has only three sections for each grade level, a total of 9, and only nine teachers were able to participate in this study.

3.2 Research Design

In this study, a descriptive phenomenological design is being used. This kind of qualitative research methodology is focused on comprehending the actual experiences that certain people have with particular circumstances. The goal of this strategy is to give a thorough explanation of the particular scenario as it is perceived by the participants. This approach is being used impartially and without bias (Delve & Limpaecher, 2022), and the results are not influenced by any associated theories or beliefs.

We interviewed instructors in-depth for this study in order to assess their perceptions of the MTB-MLE curriculum. While collecting our data, we ran into a few problems. First, some of the questions weren't addressed clearly and concisely; second, people thought the questions were similar, particularly the first three research questions; and third, there was a particular teacher who was just getting started in the field.

- 1.) Specifying: The participants found the questions difficult to understand. They provided thoughtful responses, although it is understandable that they found it difficult to provide precise answers to some queries, particularly for teachers with years of experience and longevity in the field. They conveyed a great deal of information in an understandable manner.
- 2.) Similar questions: some participants thought the questions were the same, while others realized that they were still specific. They all provided a thorough justification for their points, and they all presented a clear explanation.
- 3.) New teacher: Due to her recent entry into the profession, this participant in particular found it difficult to respond to the questions. Despite having a different experience from other educators with years of expertise in the field, she was still able to give her personal perspective and the experiences she had while teaching MTB-MLE.

In order to solve these issues, we made sure that the participants understood the significance of the study and its goal. We also reassured them about the steps we had taken to protect their privacy and cause the least amount of interruption.

In our study, we conducted in-depth interviews among the teachers using a specific set of questions from Grades 1 to 3 since they are the ones that is directly involved in the implementation of the Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education (MTB-MLE) curriculum. Our analysis of the interview revealed that teachers loved the idea that MTB-MLE curriculum included the local languages and cultures but others expressed their concerns about the lack of training for teachers as well as resources in teaching. The teachers have different sentiments regarding the language transitioning design of the curriculum. For them, the transition is effective because it improves language skills of the learners while other finds it sudden because there is not enough support for the learners. The participants identified several challenges in implementing the MTB-MLE curriculum, including lack of resources, lack of trainings and seminars for teachers, and lack of books that is translated already in mother tongue. Many participants reported

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positive impacts of the MTB-MLE curriculum on students' learning and engagement. However, some expressed concerns about learners' proficiency in the national language which is English. Our analysis concludes that, despite the MTB-MLE curriculum's potential to improve student learning and engagement, there are important implementation-related issues that must be resolved.

4.FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Effects of MTB-MLE in primary education in terms of Curriculum, Instruction and Assessment

In terms of: RQ1	Theme Cluster	Emergent Themes
Effects of MTB-MLE in primary education in terms of Curriculum, Instruction and Assessment	Success Easy Understanding of Concepts Enhance Students' Engagement	Benefits of MTB-MLE Program
	Struggles Linguistic Problems Transition Challenges	Mother Tongue as the Language of Instruction
	No Codified Dialect in Davao Region	Difference between Sinugboanong Binisaya and Local Bisaya Dialect Inadequacy of Instructional
	Inadequate Instructional Materials	Materials in MTB-MLE Program
	Construction of non-standardized test	
	Teacher Training Difficulty	Training Needs of Faculty

In Table 1, the emergent themes and their corresponding clustered themes are listed. The emergent themes represent overarching concepts or categories that emerged from the data analysis, while the clustered themes are more specific subcategories or dimensions within each emergent theme. It contains the success and struggles as shared by the participants as they implement the MTB-MLE in terms of curriculum, instruction, and assessment.

For instance, in **“The effects of MTB-MLE Program in Primary Education in terms of Curriculum, Instruction, and Assessment”** which encompasses success and struggles experienced by the teachers, the findings reveal that the Mother Tongue as the Language Transitioning Design for Basic Education has its success and struggles encountered by grade one to three teachers in Dawis Elementary School. The responses were arranged according to the success to provide a full picture of their experiences then followed by the struggles they encountered during the implementation.

The success with its emergent theme which is the benefits of MTB-MLE Program includes success in terms of **curriculum, instruction and assessment** which are the following; **easy understanding of concepts and enhance students' engagement** that teachers from grades one to three recognizes when the MTB-MLE program were properly implemented and supported, providing the appropriate language for the subject matter.

According to the three (3) grade 2 teachers, participants 5, 4, and 6 in Dawis Elementary School in terms of **curriculum** it is easier for the learners to understand the lessons as they are using their first language in their class as indicated in the response below: **“Sa mga lessons kay mas dali mi magka sinabot sa mga bata kay pinulongan nato.” (Even though making the switch might be hard, teaching in a language they're more familiar with can make a big difference.)** – Line 1, Participant 5

Also, according to participant 6 and 4 it easy for them to understand the concepts in their lesson utilizing the MTB-MLE in their class.

“Sa curriculum advantages sa grade one and grade two kay masabtan nila ang lesson. Dili naka mu translate ug Bisaya. Advantages makasabot man tuod sila.” (Then in terms of curriculum, it is an advantage for both grades 1 and 2 because they can easily

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understand the lesson. You do not need to translate in Bisaya. The advantage is they can understand it in discussions.) – Line 1-3, Participant 6

“In terms of curriculum, inig transition sa mga bata gikan sa lower grades padulong sa higher grades mas masabtan na nila ma master na nila satoa palang inistoryahan bago sila mo kuan sa english so mao pud na ang positive notes pag butang sa mother tongue.” (In the curriculum, the positive aspect is that the aim of implementing mother tongue education is to facilitate a smoother transition for students as they progress from lower to higher grades. They can better understand concepts in their mother tongue before transitioning to English. This is a positive outcome of introducing mother tongue education into the curriculum.) – Line 1-4, Participant 4

Additionally, participant 8 claims to have a similar experience, whereas the MTB-MLE is clearly a significant aid for the learners as they are able to understand the lessons being given with ease.

“Okay sa instruction, this is good as to the instruction because we’re using the mother tongue the Cebuano the Bisaya language to teach and also, okay sa success sa mga bata sa mga learners they will easily understand the lesson and also to the teacher yes it is very easy also because no need for you to explain it in english or other that you need to explain, the delivery of the lesson dili na mag effort kaayo ang teacher sa pag tudlo it’s because diretso na siya Bisaya.” (This is also true for instruction. It’s good for teaching because we use Cebuano or Bisaya, the mother tongue, to teach. This method helps students or learners do well because they can easily understand the lessons. It enables the teachers, too, because they don’t have to describe things in English or another language. Since the lesson is in Bisaya, the teacher can do little work to teach it). – Line 1, Participant 8

In terms of curriculum the first emergent theme is related to the **easy understanding of the concept**. According to Briggs (2001), Deller and Rinvoluceri (2002), Galali and Cinkara (2017), and Briggs (2001), L1 plays an essential role to second language acquisition in the classroom. Seftiawan (2018) asserts that six-year-old students can acquire a second language and develop their vocabulary through translation with the aid of their mother tongue. According to Hanáková and Metruk (2017), L1 can also be used to check learners' comprehension as well as to clarify specific vocabulary, grammar, directions, and organizational goals. Alshehri (2017), who noted that L1 in a second language classroom builds strong relationships with pupils, likewise holds this opinion. It leads learners to easily understand the subject matter being taught since their first language is being utilized as medium of instruction.

Moreover, in terms of **enhancing students’ engagement** utilizing MTB- MLE, the participants said that MTB-MLE it enhances the interaction between the teachers and the learners. The language storytelling makes it simple for children to communicate and can confidently convey their thoughts and insights about the story as they utilized their first language in speaking. This is evident in the response according to participant number 7 and 8 a grade three teachers.

“So ang success sa MTB example kanang language na storytelling dali lang maka communicate ang bata, dali na masabtan, dali nila ma answer kung storytelling siya kay mother tongue man maka express dayun sila so naa silay confidence na tama kay wala man silay wrong grammar kay ilaha mang language.” (I will begin with success, so success in MTB (Mother Tongue-Based) examples such as language storytelling makes it simple for children to communicate, understand rapidly, and respond to questions when they are told stories. Because they can confidently convey themselves in their native language, they do not worry about grammatical errors.) – Line 1, Participant 7

“This program is really good this is for the improvement of the learners it improves their interaction with us and also to the teachers this is to make the job the teaching easier because of the language the use of this language and for the learners also it will give more benefits for the learners.” (This program is excellent. This is for the growth of both the students and the teachers. For the teachers, it will make their jobs more manageable because of the language. For the students, it will give them more benefits.) – Line 1, Participant 8

The outcomes reported above indicate that participant 7 can clearly relate to the advantages of implementing the MTB-MLE program since students find it easy to understand the teachers' instructions.

“So pag hatag og instruction sa mga bata dali ra kay Bisaya man mother tongue man. Kana lang siya ang advantage kung mag hatag instruction dali ra masabtan, and ang story pud.” (So, when you give them directions in their native language, it’s much easier for them to understand. In a story, they can easily understand what is written). – Line 1, Participant 7

The findings reveal that the **Mother Tongue as the Language Transitioning Design for Basic Education** has its success and struggles encountered by grade one to three teachers in Dawis Elementary School. The success in terms of **curriculum, instruction**

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and assessment resulted in **deeper understanding of concepts** and **enhances students' engagement**. Teachers from grades one to three recognize the MTB-MLE curriculum's benefits and high success rate when properly implemented and supported, providing the appropriate language for the subject matter. The language storytelling makes it simple for children to communicate and can confidently convey their thoughts and insights about the story as they utilized their first language in speaking. Students can easily understand and the children are more articulate. They realized that building students' trust when using MTBMLE for classroom communication is essential. By simplifying difficult lessons, MTB-MLE improved student knowledge sharing, classroom engagement, interest, and learning (Gaylo, 2020). According to participants, students improved academically, gained a deeper understanding of the material, actively participated in class discussions, freely expressed their thoughts and ideas, and gained self-confidence utilizing their first language as a mode of instruction (Aliab et al., 2018).

Proceeding with the difficulties, in the setbacks of MTB-MLE as transitioning design for basic education in terms of the struggles with its emergent themes such as mother tongue as the language of instruction, difference between Sinugboanong Binisaya and local Bisaya dialect, inadequacy of instructional materials in MTB-MLE program, and training needs of faculty. These emergent themes deals with different hurdles such as **linguistic problems, transition challenges, construction of non-standardized test and inadequate instructional materials, teacher training difficulty, and no codified dialect in Davao Region**. This was being observed based on the experiences of the grades one to three teachers in Dawis Elementary School.

First are the **linguistic problem and transition challenges**, according to a statement from a grade two teacher in Dawis Elementary School, the terminologies being used in mathematics are longer when translated from English to Sinugboanong Binisaya. Consequently, the instructor had to put in additional effort translating words from Sinugboanong Binisaya to English because the students were using standard English terminology for mathematics classes. Translating common terminology into one's native tongue has an impact on the learning process for both teachers and students. This was expressed by participant number 4 a grade two teacher, stating thus.

“Mao na akong mga difficulty, unsa maning mga terminology kanang usa, duha, tulo ... gusto nako nga hanas na sila og english kay para dili sila makalitan sa transition labi na sa Math, sa mga terms na english gyud kanang addition, subtraction, plus, minus, kanang kuhaan, dungagan, pilo- piluon ... labi na gumunhap na term sa bisaya kanang mga ing ana, mao to nag lisud ko mao na akoang in terms of instruction. Kanang by word jud ka mag translate sa uban kay naa baya mga bata noh nga sailang balay palang daan ba kanang ilang mga ginatan-aw english mahimo na nuon siya murag burden sailaha na mag tuon pa sila og laglom na Bisaya. So mao na nga mga struggles na encounter sa instruction.” (This was when I ran into difficulties. I had to figure out what words meant, like "usa," "duha," and "tulo," and I wanted to help my kids improve. Since they were in third grade, I wanted to improve their English skills to help them with the change, especially in areas like math where words like "addition," "subtraction," "plus," "minus," and others are important. I worked hard to ensure they didn't have any trouble, especially with word problems. It also took a lot of work to translate everything directly into English. Some students spoke English at home, so it could be hard for them to learn complex words in Bisaya. These were the problems I had in instruction.)
– Line 1-2, Participant 4

As per Mahboob and Cruz (2013), one of the primary issues

We give too much weight to the foreign language when counting numbers in the Philippines, especially when it comes to the mother tongue education. We never really use our local language for this purpose. They added that Filipino and other regional languages are marginalized in the Philippines, where English is seen as the primary language. Cebuanos prefer to use English over their mother tongue, according to Dr. Yolanda S. Quijano, Director of the DepEd Bureau of Elementary Education. The teachers also became aware of the MTB-MLE's application restrictions when they observed that not all ideas in mathematics and the natural sciences could be taught using the MTB-MLE and lack the vocabulary needed to translate words between English and Filipino (Medilo, 2017).

In similar with this study, participant number 1 reveals that the underlying concern upon implementing MTB-MLE in primary education is the complexity of the terminologies being used especially in mathematics classes.

“Pero mao lage to akong ingon nga ang ako lang man gyung problema is kanang sa math. Kay ang mga bata nako kasagaran mas naanad man gud sila ug English nga term. So, kung naay mga for example 1 fourth 1 half ikuan nimo siya, imoha siyang i-translate so muagi jud ka ug translation. Murag ikuan gyud nimo ang kuan gani sa bata schema niya himayon jud nimo.” (But as what I have said, my problem is in the Math subject because my pupils are more used to using English terms in numbers. For example, 1 fourth 1 half you should translate it. You will really undergo translation first. You should apply or give a schema to the children.) - Line 1-4, Participant 1

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In fact, in the context of the Philippines, mother tongue appears to be the second language spoken by the learners, as they are utilizing mathematical terms in English rather than their mother tongues at home. Additionally, a lot of the kids became disinterested because of language barriers. Transferee students (having a different L1) find it difficult to follow the lectures and don't engage (Casalan et al., 2016). For instance, Kolman (2019) found that the textbook's usage of complex terminologies makes it difficult for teachers to teach the material to students using MTB-MLE. In order to help pupils understand, they also need to translate the complex terminology.

Second, the **lack of availability of the materials** according to Pouezevera et al. (2014), it appears to have a relationship between material availability and the content it contains especially the terms that differs with what our usual terms. As what participant number 4 experiencing the difficulty in content based on the response below.

“Difficulty is ang material lahi ang naa sa textbooks na kanang available is Sinugboanong Binisaya which is dili mao ang bisaya nga ato gyud gigamit diri. So ang ilaha naa silay mga terms diri na laglom kaayo nga dili na nato gina gamit locally saatoang lugar dinhi sa Digos. Pareha anang pag “dibuho” kay kuan drawing unya idibuho dili baya ta sa atong normal na conversation maskin inside the classroom.” (However, the challenge lies in the available materials and its content. The Sinugboanong Binisaya, which is different from the Bisaya we commonly use here in Digos, provides certain terms that are not commonly used in our local context. For instance, the term "dibuho" (drawing) wasn't widely used until the implementation of the Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education (MTB-MLE) program.) - Line 1-2, Participant 4

Given that Sinugboanong Binisaya is not their mother tongue, complex terminologies found in books and other instructional materials pose the greatest challenge to both teachers and pupils. Gaylo (2020) showed how challenging it is to accomplish MTB-MLE goals due to the limited vocabulary. Some kids might not fully understand the dialect being employed. Adriano et al. (2021) noted a number of challenges, including an absence of dictionaries and textbooks, that made it especially challenging to teach and have quick success with MTB-MLE adoption since teachers are not familiar with the language.

Furthermore, the disadvantage of assessment in mother tongue as the transitioning design for basic education in terms of the theme **construction of non-standardized test**. The participant reveals that they encounter difficulties during assessments since it was constructed by complex terminologies that may affect the learner's academic performance.

“Didto lang ka mag problema pag naay mga unfamiliar words gamiton nimo sa assessment maka affect jud sailang score. Dili man nato ma expect tanan mga bata na makasabot jud sila noh, above average noh, usually mga bata diri noh naa jud sa average, daghan jud nag below average nga mga bata. Although gitudlo na nimo na pag abot sa exam, nakalimot na. So diha mo exert jud og effort, dapat naay mga strategy ang mga teacher ana. Sa assessment okay lang, makasabot pero naa gyud uban na di makasabot. Walay retention ang uban, pag exam wala gihapon so kailangan mag exert effort ang teacher ma superpower. (It only becomes a problem when the test uses words they don't know, which can significantly affect their marks. You can only expect some kids to understand some things because only some are entirely above average. Most kids usually do about average, and quite a few do worse. Even if you teach them, they might need to remember when the test comes. So, the teacher needs to work harder in that area. There ought to be plans in place. It's okay for grading purposes; some students get it, but some don't. Some students need help remembering what they've learned, so they still have trouble on tests. That's why teachers have to work harder—it's like having a superpower!) Line 1-5, Participant 8

According to Brown (2003), assessment is a continuous process that covers a far larger range of topics. The manner in which assessments are conducted varies based on the situation and the goals that must be met. But the issue of what and how to practice and measure the specific outcome in a classroom emerges. Furthermore, a number of factors, from the curriculum and how it is implemented in the classroom, to the way the teachers carry out the lesson that is in line with the policy's outcomes, or how the assessment procedures relate to the lessons that have been taught, it has a significant impact on the implementation of MTB-MLE since assessments became more complex because of the terminologies being used. According to Genon and Torres (2015), assessments can take many in the case of implementing the MTB-MLE learners academic performance were greatly affected during examinations.

In addition, **the teacher and training difficulty** in a research study by Abrea et al., 2021, it is said in the discussion and findings that teachers should receive MTB-MLE training and transition techniques to help them better transition students. Teachers who are teaching multilingual students need training and seminars because they need to be guided and orientated on how to deal with students who speak multiple languages.

This aligns with observations found in the participant number 6 responses below.

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“The difficulties of the teachers when the teachers maka encounter silag mutudlog MTB pag wala gani sila naka seminar jud. Sa katong permero jud nga training maglisod gyud ang teacher labina ang makita nimo na didto sa libro ang kuan nila halas for example, halas bitin na siya sa atoa. So, naa na siyay bali naa na siyay language barrier na nahitabo. So, diha na ang bata ma confuse so amo nalang ikuan ipasabot iexplain.” **(The difficulties of the teachers are when they teach MTB and they weren't able to attend seminars about it. If they weren't able to attend seminars or trainings, they will really find it difficult to teach. Especially when we see in the book the word halas. Halas is a term in sinugbuanong binisaya which means snake in english. In our term, it is called bitin. That situation now can cause language barrier because that is the time that the kids will get really confused. So, we just try to explain to them slowly.)** – Line 1-3, Participant 6

Instructors found it challenging to teach MTB-MLE lessons, particularly when using unfamiliar language. They find it challenging to converse in the Cebu dialect known as Sinugbuanong Binisaya. The students' lack of prior exposure with a different language makes it difficult carry the lesson effectively. According to Sumalinog (2018), the terminologies used in the teaching aids are not translated locally, which makes it difficult for teachers to use them. Furthermore, Dumetz et al. (2021) observed that students learning concurrent languages faced difficulties and considered the lectures more difficult to understand. One of the participants' challenges was validated by the latter assertion.

Moreover, the findings of this study have resulted upon the implementation of MTB-MLE as transitioning design for basic education that there were **no codified dialect and orthographies** were provided in Davao Region that leads to confusion of the teachers in Dawis Elementary School. The terminologies in Sinugboanong Binisaya are far different from the local language used in the community. Instructors found it challenging to teach MTB-MLE lessons, particularly when using unfamiliar language. They find it challenging to converse in the Cebu dialect known as Sinugbuanong Binisaya. This was revealed by the participant number 4, 7, 1, 3 and 8.

“Difficulty is ang material na kanang available is Sinugboanong Binisaya which is dili mao ang bisaya nga ato gyud gigamit diri. So ang ilaha naa silay mga terms diri na laglom kaayo nga dili na nato gina gamit locally saatoang lugar dinhi sa Digos. Pareha anang pag “dibuho” kay kuan drawing unya idibuho dili baya ta sa atong normal na conversation maskin inside the classroom.” **(However, the challenge lies in the available materials. The Sinugboanong Binisaya, which is different from the Bisaya we commonly use here in Digos, provides certain terms that are not commonly used in our local context. For instance, the term "dibuho" (drawing) wasn't widely used until the implementation of the Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education (MTB-MLE) program.)** – Line 1-4, Participant 4

“Ang struggle ani niya is example wala tay, ang Davao del Sur ang Region 11 na bisaya ang binisaya nato kay dili baya ni permanent kinuha ni sa Cebu na bisaya kaayo unya dili gyud siya original na Binisaya maglisud ang uban bata sa mga terms.” **(The Bisaya spoken in Davao is not identical to the Bisaya spoken in Cebu; it is not the original Bisaya spoken in Mindanao. It appears that there is a mixture as a result the children sometimes can't communicate their thoughts.)** – Line 2, Participant 7

According to Medilo (2016), teachers have more complex tasks than before because of the implementation of MTB-MLE curriculum. Language was regarded by Asfaha (2020) as a crucial component of learning. The general public and other ethnic groups in the Davao Region are unfamiliar with Sinugbuanong Bisaya. For them, the experience of blending languages is bewildering. Language teaching has been confounded by MTB-MLE as a subject and even as an instructional medium, especially in public schools. Instructors found it difficult to teach pupils in the languages they were taught. Since Filipino and English are already languages spoken at home and at school, both teachers and students found teaching or learning them to be easier. The addition of MTB-MLE complicates education. Thus, MTB-MLE turns into a hurdle as opposed to a learning bridge.

On top of that, similar findings were found about the matter of the teachers encountering foreign words based on Sinugboanong Binisaya, which originates in Cebu and is not often used in the Davao Region. This is where the confusion started as stated below by participant 1, 3 and 8.

“Naay mga words nga dli siya applicable sa atoa because ang amoa man gong gi base is Sinugbuanong Binisaya which is from Cebu. So, naay mga words like for instance, kaka which is kaka is damang. Foreign sa mga bata namo because kay ang kaka ang nailhan baya nato is damang. So, kami as teacher, so nag adjust mi kay naay mga words nga dili namo familiar.” **(There are words that is not applicable to us because this is sinugbuanong binisaya which is from Cebu. So, there are words like for instance, kaka which means spider in English. It is foreign for the pupils because kaka is damang in Bisaya and damang is the word**

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that the kids are used to hearing. So, we teachers, we really adjusted cause there are words that we are not familiar with.) – Line 2-5, Participant 1

“There are some terminologies sa mother tongue which is lahi man gud ang Sinugbuanong Binisaya compared dire sa Dabawenyong. There are words nga lahi ba lahi ang meaning kami as teacher, mag translate pajud mi daghan mig kanang i-translate pa namo pag ayo para lang jud masabtan sa bata”. **(The negative side is that, there are some terminologies in the mother tongue of Cebu which is the Sinugbuanong Binisaya that is very different from the binisaya here in Dabawenyong. There are words that is different in meaning. Teachers really need to make the pupils understand it. We teachers really need to translate so that they can understand the lesson.)** – Line 1-3, Participant 3

The hurdle for teachers and students when using Sinugbuanong Binisaya instructional resources, such books, is understanding the complex terminology since it is not their first language. Gaylo (2020) showed how challenging it is to accomplish MTB-MLE goals due to the limited vocabulary. There's a chance that some pupils don't fully understand the terminology being utilized. Adriano et al. (2021) noted a number of challenges, including a dearth of dictionaries and textbooks, that made it especially challenging to teach and have quick success with MTB-MLE adoption since teachers are not familiar with the language.

Another similar finding has yielded the same concern as stated by participant 8 where Davao Region don't have its orthography and find it difficult following the Sinugboanong Binisaya which is from Cebu.

“But then to the struggles is since diri sa Davao Region wala man ta nag gamit wala man ta ni follow gyud. Wala man tay atoang kanang Binisaya nga atoa gyud kaning gigamit na Binisaya diri karon is kananang nag based didto sa Sinugboanong Binisaya, gi based ddo sa Cebu murag usage sa Cebu. Mas ma exert napud og mohatag napud og effort ang teacher sa pag memorize ana it's because kita mismo malibog, dili nata fluent ana, dili naman ta fluent ani kay wa kay gi gamit so mao na siya ang struggles.” **(But the problem is that in the Davao Region, we haven't always used the same kind of Bisaya that we use now. The one used is based on Sinugboanong Binisaya from Cebu, which is used similarly to Cebuano. It is a deeper and more traditional form of Bisaya. The problem is that we must follow the syllabus, which tells us what language and words to use when teaching.)** –Line 1-2, Participant 8

Other than that, participant 8 had the experience of teaching in Tudaya, where 99% of the population is Bagubo and Bisaya is not their first language. Utilizing MTB-MLB in a setting where learners' first language does not correspond with the material presents a significant challenge for both teachers and learners. In relation with this, the participant's response below is concerned about the fact that the Bisaya spoken in the Davao Region differs from that spoken in Sinugboanong Binisaya.

“Asa ko mamoblema, walay original na language gikan gyud diri gi kuha rana siya sa Cebu bisan pag bisaya didto pero lahi ang pag ka bisaya compared diri sa Davao Region. Sa mga bukid bukid for example sa Tudaya, naka try man kog tudlog tudaya ddo permiro ko kuan naka tudlo MTB, 99% ang population ddo Bagubo pure jud Bagubo dili kaayo sila kuan sa bisaya, ang gigamit namo kay MTB-MLE bisaya baya ddo kay di man mi mgga Bagubo ang teachers samot nag kalibog, kulang pa jud sa materials pero ana man jud i embrace lang. Dili first language bisaya ang sa mga kuan diri sa Davao Region. Mag adjust ang teacher asta ang mga bata.” **(The difficulty arises because there is no specific term for these concepts in the Davao Region's original language, which appears to be a hybrid, somewhat like an adopted variant of Cebuano, even though it is taught in Bisaya. I have attempted to teach in rural areas such as Tudaya, where the majority of the population is Bagobo. Due to their limited Bisaya proficiency, we employ MTB-MLE (Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education) in Bisaya despite the difficulty it presents. Bisaya is not the native tongue of youth in the Davao Region. Teachers and students must both make appropriate adjustments.)** – Line 4-7, Participant 8

In addition to taking into account their suggestions for a more successful MTB-MLE implementation, the Department of Education must set up procedures to uphold instructors' generally positive behaviors (Agbayani, n.d.). It highlights the fact that education won't be completed until pupils have a solid connection to their mother tongue and culture (Mangila, 2018). The Department of Education (DepEd) has to keep creating trustworthy teaching resources to help instructors with their everyday indigenous language education.

Since Sinugbuanong Binisaya is not a functioning language in the Davao region, it is really difficult for both teachers and learners. It is hoped that the language being utilized is the real spoken language in the community because it would be much easier for the learners to learn as well as for teachers to teach if that is the case. Considering local writers in the localization of instructional materials and the orthography of the dialect used locally is suggested. Other than that, they suggested that legislators do a comprehensive analysis of the MTB-MLE policy and for its effectiveness to significantly affect the growth of students' knowledge

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(Gempeso & Mendez (2021). Speaking of students' knowledge, most of the learners still learn through classroom instruction (Horwitz, 2008), that is why this should be highly considered by legislators and policy makers since we are talking about the effective way to teach and learn.

The Effects of the Transition from Mother Tongue to English Language to the Learners

In terms of RQ2:	Theme Cluster	Emergent Themes
Effects of the transition from Mother Tongue to English Language to the learners	Lexical Problems Lack of Instructional Materials Translation difficulties Comprehension difficulties	Adverse Effect of the Linguistic Transition

The third emergent theme in "The Effects of the transition from Mother Tongue to English Language to the Learners," in terms of the **impact of language linguistic transition** which includes subcategories such as **lexical problems, lack of instructional materials, translation difficulties, and comprehension difficulties**. These themes highlight the recurring problems during the transition from Mother Tongue to English language. The teachers run into challenges in **lexical problems** emphasizing the problem in vocabulary.

The teachers run into challenges in **lexical problems** emphasizing the problem in vocabulary. This is evident in the statement below of participant number 2, a grade one teacher.

"Laglom nga binisaya o Sinugbuanong Binisaya. Makakuha man sila kanang parehas sa kuan atoa diba langka nang prutas, tas nangka atoa o ana sila. Unsa gani to kanang kaka kaila mog kaka damang o damang ana. Ipakita nimo na nga picture muana sila damang, damang jud ay mag lisod. Kaka ni siya unya wala ko kabalo nganong na kaka mani asa mani gikan. Asa jud gani na nag origin. O kita di baya na in ana atoa damang baya na."

(There are deep Bisaya words or Sinugbuanong Binisaya. They can understand it like for example in Sinugbuanong Binisaya the word langka (jackfruit) it is a fruit and then nangka is our term in our Bisaya language. So, it is quite similar at some point. Another term is kaka (spider). In our language that is called damang. If you show them a picture of a kaka, the kids will immediately say damang because that is what they are used to. I do not even know why it is called kaka. I don't know where it is from where it is originated.) – Line 1-7, Participant 2

According to the study conducted by Bajas et al. (2017), this phenomenon is sometimes referred to as a deficiency in appropriate vocabulary to effectively communicate a message or transmit information. One of the challenges encountered by educators in teaching the mother tongue pertains to the limited range of terminology or phrases available for discourse during instructional sessions. Another thing is that the availability of educational resources and qualified teachers who are fluent in the local tongues is one such difficulty (Benson, 2019). It is not justifiable for them to assert that their vocabulary is sufficient, as their students do not possess fluency in the widely spoken language and not all terms in the target language have direct translations in the students' mother tongue. Furthermore, barriers to the general implementation of MTB-MLE programs include worries about standardized testing, switching to other languages, and social views toward indigenous languages (McCarty, 2011).

In addition, **lack of reading/instructional materials** as per participant number 6, a grade three teacher in Dawis Elementary School, stated that one of the problems or factors that should be paid attention to is textbooks. She stated that:

"So ang kuan jud isa jud ana ang kuan ang atoang textbooks. Tapos dapat naa pud untay dictionary ba nga gihubad na daan kay nag depende ta sa Sinugbuanong Binisaya, unya dire satoa sa Davao, lahi man pud atoa so diha magka problema. So, mao unta kanang kumpleto na sa instructional materials ba ana jud." **(So, one of the problems or factors that should be paid attention to is textbooks. There should be a dictionary that translates every single word for us because we depend on Sinugbuanong Binisaya and here in Davao, it is different from the language that we are used to so that is the problem. There should be complete instructional materials to all teachers and for those teachers that is teaching MTB there should also be trainings for them.)** – Line 1-3, Participant 6

Bjas et al. (2017) say teachers and students struggle with this. Instructors were particularly affected because they teach and students rely on their conversations. The participants complained about the books' content. Students find these works' terminology

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challenging and often objectionable. Since the writer's language is foreign, the teacher worries that students won't understand some terminology. Text terminology can be confusing even for teachers. Gaylo (2020) demonstrated that the limited vocabulary makes implementing MTB-MLE goals difficult. Certain students may have limited comprehension of the language being used. Adriano et al. (2021) identified several difficulties, such as a lack of textbooks and dictionaries, that made it particularly difficult to teach and achieve immediate success with MTB-MLE implementation, as teachers are unfamiliar with the terminology used. Using a familiar language makes learning much more accessible. As a result, instructional materials' shortcomings require attention and correction, as students and teachers rely on these tools to acquire knowledge.

Moreover, we have **translation difficulties** and **comprehension problems**. These problems are the ones that the teachers really find as a huge problem since these problems really means that they have to put more effort into teaching as well as use some new strategies that might make the students comprehend, and for them to also understand the discussion/lesson better.

Translation difficulties was one of the problems encountered during the class discussions. There are difficulties in translating Sinugbuanong Binisaya into student-friendly terms. However, teachers of MTB-MLE frequently used translation as a strategy to aid in comprehension during lessons. According to participant number 1, a grade one teacher.

“Kuan ang recurring problema nila is kanang naay mga words nga syempre kay lahi man sa English lahi sa Filipino lahi sa Bisaya, naay mga words nga lahi ug meaning sa Bisaya lahi ug meaning sa English, so as a teacher, iano jud nimo na siya kanang tanan nimong buhaton murag mahulog jud nga I do, we do, explicit teaching. So, I, teacher first, we, sila with teacher, and you, sila nalang. Dapat be specific jud ka the way you teach and then dapat naa gyud kay key picture. Kay sa grade 1 ang bata man gud is auditory visual and tactics kanang mahikapan nila ba dili kay pure on words lang ka.” **(The recurring problem is that, there are words that is different in meaning. It is different in English, in Filipino as well as in Bisaya. There are words that is different in meaning in Bisaya and also different in meaning in the English language. So as a teacher, you should really do this what we call explicit teaching. I do, we do, you do. So, I teacher first, we teacher with the children, and lastly you the pupils alone. You should be specific in the way you teach and you should also have key picture because grade 1 pupils are auditory and visual learners. You should present or show them tangible objects or things to represent your examples. You shouldn't rely in teaching thru words alone.)** – Line 1-4, Participant 1

Teachers who borrow and translate materials from one language to another improve students' comprehension of the lessons (Kolman, 2019). The translation is significant because it can assist in meeting the needs of students who speak a variety of languages. Maeikien (2019) and Parba (2018) emphasized that translation answers all teachers' challenges when teaching MTB-MLE. The translation is highly beneficial in learning using the students' native language because it links the students and the lesson.

When teachers have difficulties in translating or in conducting an effective instruction, **comprehension problems** will surely occur in the classroom. Makar (2005) said that the students have difficulty in correctly reading information. Being unfamiliar with certain terms will really make it hard for students to understand what they read and grasp certain concepts and discussions. Participant number 4, a grade two teacher can attest to this.

“...kasagaran sakong mga estudyante maskin mga utokan sila gagmay silag kuha sa mother tongue kay murag too much gud sailaha ang kuan nag kanang wordings. Diba pag i translate nato ang English into mother tongue mas taas man siya, para mas masabtan nila. Promise kay kasagaran mga top students nako noh ang mother tongue gyud nila ang ilahang kryptonite baba kaayo nila ang mother tongue.” **(My students often have trouble with the mother tongue subject assessment. Even the smartest students sometimes have trouble with it because the words can be hard for them to understand. When we translate English into the mother tongue, the level of difficulty tends to increase, in order to make it more understandable for them. Surprisingly, many of my top pupils seem to have the most trouble with the subject of their mother tongue, as if it becomes their weak point. They seem to get confused by how hard the language is to understand.)** -Line 1-4, Participant 4

Trujillo (2020) recommended that teachers strictly enforce the first language as the medium of instruction from the start for students to express their ideas clearly and think without hesitation or self-doubt. However, the statements made by the teachers above just simply means that there is really a need of strategies in teaching that has to be incorporated in conducting classes such as, differentiated instruction: where they create a plan that includes extra practice, step-by-step directions and special homework. This is closely in-line with the study of Sanders & Rivers, 1996; Wright, Horn & Sanders, 1997; Rockoff, 2004, that improving the quality or effectiveness of teachers will support achievement of students.

Teaching Strategies to Address the Challenges in the Transition from Mother Tongue to English Language

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In terms of RQ3:	Theme Cluster	Emergent Themes
The strategies that teachers address about the transition from Mother Tongue to English language	Translation of target language to mother Tongue Utilization of Multilingual Resources Utilization of technological aids Use of scaffolding and bridging in instruction Enhancing and optimizing the learning experience of students	Strategies for Transition Adaptation

Furthermore, "**The Teachers Strategies addressing the Challenges brought by the Transition from Mother Tongue to English for Students' Performance,**" with the emergence of **strategies for transition adaptation** which involves **translation of target language to mother tongue, utilization of multilingual resources, utilization of technologies aids, and use of scaffolding and bridging in instruction, enhancing and optimizing the learning experience of students.** This theme emphasizes the strategies to address the challenges in the implementation of MTB-MLE program.

First, it is very important to do **translation of target language to mother tongue in teaching.** According to Abao et al. (2016), children's mother tongue development is a reliable indicator of how well they would acquire a second language. It also shows that using L2 and L3 as a tool improves their vocabulary and helps them understand the teachings. In order to help students grasp the lecture better, teachers translate for them. For this reason, it is regarded as an essential component of instruction in a classroom. The motivation for the policy is that learning in a language familiar to the child helps establish a strong foundation for further education and literacy development. Through this strategy, it will be very easy for the teachers to teach and make the learners understand the words that teachers utter and, in that way, learners will understand the discussion better Ocampo (2006).

The participants believe that translation is crucial. Teachers should also adapt the lecture into every student's native tongue to ensure greater comprehension. The statement of participant 1 and 2, both grade one teachers make this clear:

"Dapat the way you teach is kanang masabtan. Concrete and then kung pwede brief pero concise and if the learners are not able to understand yet better give another example para mas masabtan and then sa akoang klase, Then kuan na concrete objects." **(You should teach in a concrete way so that pupils will better understand the lesson and if possible. Then you really need to have concrete objects for example, in Math, you've got to have things for counting.)**

"Mag provide jud kag pictures sa ilaha para ma picture out nila kung unsa imohang pasabot. Mas masabtan man gud nila basta naay pictures. And again, translation ug naa silay dili masabtan nga word or term pasabton jud nimo sila in a slow way para ma gets jud nila ang meaning." **(You should provide pictures to them so that they will be able to picture out what you are trying to say or what you mean to say to them and that will enable them to understand better. And again translation. If there is a term or word that they find difficult and doesn't understand the meaning, you should help them in a slow manner so that they will really understand the meaning of it.)** – Line 1-4, Participant 1

"Mag translate gyud ko kailangan jud siyag translation pero lage katong akong ingon nga nakatabang pud baya gyud sya like mao ni akong unsa satong NLC karon o na mga gipili baya na atong mga dili gyud kabalo nga bata mao na akong gamit kay mother tongue gyud kay mas makahatag man sila." **(I should really translate. It is really crucial. As what I have said earlier, that this is quite helpful like this is what also shows or is similar to our NLC now. Those frustrated learners are chosen and mother tongue is the language that I really use because they can give more insights and answers.)** – Line 1, Participant 2

The study of Besinga, M. E. (2019) in the Barangay of Magroyong of San Miguel Surigao del Sur, Philippines stated that majority of the teachers in the classroom said that the best tactic was to translate from the target language into the mother tongue.

Second, **utilization of multilingual resources.** The educational basics - textbooks, learning materials - should be available in mother-tongue languages as well because the unavailability of appropriate literature and instructional materials is often identified as a constraint in the development of a localized curriculum (Annayat and Rasak, 2021). Having the necessary materials specifically supporting materials, is really needed for the learners to have a basis and guide in their learning journey. It makes it easy for teachers to teach because there will be a form of material that they will carry or handle wherever they go, and it makes it easy for them to access the activities given by the teacher anytime anywhere since it is tangible.

According to participant number 4, a grade two teacher stated below.

“I-translate nimo into english kay para dili kaayo kurat sailaha nga sa pag ka grade four pa nila mahibal-an ng ang english sa ponglihok kay verb.. ang kaka spider na siya kay basig sailang huna huna ba damang kay kaka lang gihapon ilang tawag inig abot sa grade four na spider na didto pag abot so imo pud ipasabot sailaha nga inig ka grade four in ani na.. saimoha pa lang daan naka translate na siya, nakabalo na sila unsay binisaya unsay in-english thru explicit teaching.” **(That's what I meant by "teaching clearly." This method makes it much easier for students to learn a new language. For example, they might not know that "ponglihok" means "verb" in English when they are in Grade 4. So, it would be best if you told them that in a clear way. For example, you can say, "In Grade Four, 'kaka' becomes spider in English." So, you're preparing them for the changes in words that will happen in Grade 4.)** – Line 2-5, Participant 4

Multilingual resources are not just about specific tangible things. It is also about giving a lot of options to learners. With that free will that a teacher establishes in the classroom, the learners can do what they want while also giving their best potential in what they always do since they will now have the courage because they are able to do something that is comfortable and suitable for them. According to Aliab, Prudente, & Aguila, 2018, students gained a deeper understanding of the lesson, participated actively in class, freely expressed their ideas, increased and strengthened their self-confidence, and improved their academic ability. We should always bear in mind that we always have to consider our learners. This is very evident on the statement below of participant 8 a grade three teacher.

“Mag hatag mig different activities kay hina man sila ana noh so mag basa basa gyud giving them different, labi na different man ang learning depende sa mga bata so mag hatag mi og kanang differentiated activities based sa performance ani nga bata unsa na level. So, i assess nimo ilang learning performance and then after that one during sa DEAR time kani na reading program, mao mana among remediations noh so tagaan nimo sila unsa tong mga activities nga makaya nila, unsa nga activities ang pwede sailaha kung asa sila dapit na level pa.” **(We offer a variety of tasks during this time because students may be at different skill levels. Personalizing the learning process is important because it considers each student's performance and skills. We have other exercises for each level of performance. After figuring out how well they are learning, we put these reading plans into place during the DEAR time (Drop Everything and Read). This is where our remediation efforts come in. We provide them with activities that match their capabilities and are suited to their current level.)** – Line 1-5, Participant 8

According to Garcia (2008) as cited by Milambiling (2011), multilingual language awareness is a necessity for teachers of multilingual students. Besides knowing about languages, subject matter, and teaching methodology, teachers should have an understanding of the political struggles and social circumstances of pupils. This strategy also allows the students to explore and learn the language of others. The main characteristic of a teacher is to be versatile in making ways to cater to the needs of the students. Therefore, being a multilingual teacher is an advantage in teaching pupils with different languages. The teacher can cater to the individual needs of the learners by translating the lessons he/she is teaching in the different mother tongues of the learners in the classroom.

In addition to the utilization of multilingual resources, **utilization of technological aids** is as vital as the said resources. It is highlighted again by participant number 8.

“In the same way, we depend on both reading activities and videos. Visual tools are a great way to help them learn; pictures and other visuals make it easier to understand. Even though not all students like multimedia lessons, many gain from them. Upgraded teaching tools are also used to get the students' attention and help them understand the lesson better, with the goal of getting them to perform better in the end.” **(By using different activities dapat naa kay mga materials pero saakoa diri dapat naa mi mga books mga materials para sailang pag basa and then more on pareha saakoa diri is more on reading with the use of the sa kanang ano videos. Mas dali sila makatuon pag naay mga pictures, mga visual sila naa pud uban na dili sila hilig ana pero mostly. Mga multimedias instructions, different learning materials and instructional use of kanang kuan pud upgraded pud ang instructional materials in which it will catch up the attention of the learners na makasabot sila saimong lesson, to achieve the high performance.)** – Line 1-4, Participant 8

In this explanation alone, we can conclude that, this kind of strategy is really the most used and the most popular strategy to teach MTB-MLE. Nowadays, technology is really advanced already and I think we all know that. That being said, technology is really helpful and can be really considered as a useful strategy in teaching. It is an advantage for teachers since all of us can access these kinds of materials in any setting. It is being used to its full potential and it is a great advantage for educators. Effective teaching requires the use of sufficient and pertinent teaching resources (Afolabi et. al., 2010). These educational resources can appeal to a variety of senses and are both enjoyable and educational. The process of teaching and learning depends heavily on instructional

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materials (Sunday & Joshua, 2010). Effective teaching requires the use of sufficient and pertinent teaching resources (Afolabi, Adeyanju, Adedapo & Falade, 2006 as quoted by Sunday & Joshua, 2010).

Fourth, we have the **use of scaffolding and bridging in instruction**. This particular strategy is utilized by participant number 4. A grade two teacher. The participant stated that,

“I haplak namo ang unsay objective karun na adlaw para kabalo sila maka set sila nga dapat mao ni among matun-an karun adlaw... mag hatag kag mga activities na syempre mo align saimohang objective unya explicit jud nimo siya pag tudlo dili kay sila pa imong pa guess-guesson kung ponglihok imong itudlo karun i introduce gyud nimo unsa ng ponglihok. (Explicit teaching is precisely what you need to do regarding teaching methods. It would be best to tell the kids exactly what you're teaching them. They might have trouble if you leave it up to them to figure it out on their own. At the moment, our classes focus on clearly teaching things. We start by telling them the day's objectives so they know what they will learn today. Then, we give you tasks that help you reach that goal. We tell them what the ideas are instead of having them figure them out on their own. When you bring up a new subject, you can't assume they already know something about it. It has to be clear, and your actions should be different so that people can better grasp the idea.) – Line 2 & 4, Participant 4

Bridging, the most frequent type of scaffolding strategies, is realized through making a connection between previous knowledge and new knowledge, referring to real life or students' personal experience, and making a conceptual map in the top-down process. The finding concurs with previous studies in that linking new information into existing ones or activating students' prior knowledge is one of the most important scaffolding strategies (e.g., Dalton-Puffer, 2007; Grossman, 2015; Mahan, 2020; Mahan et al., 2018; Tajeddin & Kamali, 2020). By gradually transferring the responsibility for learning from the teacher to the student, scaffolding is a tool used by educators to enhance student learning. This gradual release approach to scaffolding is popular in the classroom; it involves the teacher modelling a new concept, allowing students to work with the teacher in small groups, and then allowing them to work independently. The use of MTB-MLE increased students' ability to share knowledge, increased class interaction, increased students' inquisitiveness, and increased students' ability to learn faster because difficult lessons were simplified (Gaylo, 2020). Therefore, it will be easy for the students to try and work on some activities themselves.

Lastly, **enhancing and optimizing the learning experience of students**. The classroom setting is one of the key elements influencing how well students learn. Put simply, when students see their learning environment as encouraging and supportive, they learn more effectively (Dorman, Aldridge, & Fraser, 2006). According to participant number 4, a grade two teacher indicated her response below.

“I encourage lang gyud sila kung nalibog mo ani free ra kaayo mo mangutana ana ayaw lang mag hesitate to ask, ayaw isarili imong problema. Encouragement nalang siya nga mag tabanganay ang teacher, kung nag lisud mo aning unsa pangutana lang mo kay teacher kay i explain aron masabtan.” (I tell them they can ask questions if they don't understand something. Don't be afraid to ask for help, and don't hide your troubles. It's just a matter of reminding them that the teacher is there to help, and if they're having trouble, they can go to the teacher and ask for a better explanation.) – Line 1-3, Participant 4

A good learning environment is one in which students have a sense of belonging, trust others, and are inspired to take on challenges, take chances, and ask questions Bucholz and Sheffler (2009). An atmosphere like this offers opportunity for social skill development, clear learning objectives and feedback, pertinent information, and successful tactics (Weimer, 2009). When teachers enhance and optimize the learning experiences of students, the transmission of knowledge and learnings will be realized.

5. IMPLICATION AND CONCLUDING REMARKS

5.1 Implication

The study's research findings have yielded significant insights for policy, practice, theory, and forthcoming investigations. This study also looks into the various MTB-MLE implementation approaches and outcomes assessment methods for student learning, language retention, and overall academic success. It also looks at the variables that affect these models' performance, such as classroom involvement, teacher preparation, and the of the teaching materials. Since the MTB-MLE curriculum exposes pupils to learning in their mother tongue before moving on to a second language, it results in better language proficiency among students. The attitudes and challenges public educators faced when instructing MTB-MLE revealed the existence of implementation issues that need to be resolved and enhanced for the benefit of students' learning. The results of the study provide a basis for assessing or changing the MTB-MLE curriculum after it has been contextualized or localized to the language of the area.

Furthermore, lessons can be imparted efficiently and rapidly if the inadequate or nonexistent use of technology and instructional materials is addressed, teachers' creativity is encouraged and the use of efficient teaching methods and approaches Local curriculum

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writers and authors are required to develop the grammar and orthography of the local tongue. As a result, teaching aids, dictionaries, modules, books, and other resources will be produced that are contextualized and compatible with modern teaching techniques including PowerPoint presentations, multimedia, and video.

The study can point out difficulties in translating curriculum content and assessments between languages. This may draw attention to the necessity of carefully planning and modifying materials in order to preserve consistency in learning objectives. Finally, the study may offer insightful information to decision-makers, resulting in suggestions for improving or modifying the MTB- MLE curriculum. Future policy choices aimed at improving the efficiency of language transitions in basic education may be guided by this. The research intends to benefit students and the education system as a whole by examining these consequences and offering insightful contributions to the current discussion on MTB-MLE.

5.2 Concluding Remarks

This study aims to examine the various difficulties educators encounter when instructing young learners from diverse linguistic and tribal origins, with a specific emphasis on the Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education (MTB- MLE) curriculum implemented in primary schools. The results highlight the achievements and difficulties encountered while implementing MTB-MLE, specifically in Davis Elementary School. The findings of the study report comprehensively depict the successes and challenges educators and learners face in the MTB- MLE (Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual School). In terms of curriculum success, it is concluded that learners can easily understand the context of the lesson because they are using their first language as the medium of instruction, which results in easy understanding of concepts. The study shows that MTB-MLE can enhance student engagement, learning English words in their first language can help learners expand their vocabulary for there are deeper translations when we stick to Sinugboanong Binisaya which is different from the Bisaya dialect in Davao Region. Since the lessons are taught in their first language, the teacher will no longer translate the material in their class.

Moreover, when telling stories in class, students can effectively engage with their teachers. The advantages of using the mother tongue as the language transitioning design in primary education are also evident in terms of instruction, as it led to language familiarity and effective teaching because the students were able to communicate with the teachers in their mother tongue. Teachers find it easier to teach lessons when students are able to communicate in their native language since they do not need to translate and explain English words to the learners. On top of that, assessments have the same benefits as curriculum and instruction where learners can simply understand the instructions on them, which can improve their overall performance as learners.

Nevertheless, the themes mentioned above also serves to underscore the obstacles encountered by educators at Dawis Elementary School. One of the concerns may arise in curriculum where linguistic problems, transition challenges, construction of non-standardized test, lack of availability of materials, teacher training difficulty and no codified dialects in Davao Region were provided. When it comes to the mother tongue language, Sinugboanong Binisaya is used upon implementing the program in the curriculum; this makes it different from the Bisaya in Davao Region that learners commonly use, which causes the students to struggle to understand certain terminologies. Teachers had to spend extra time explaining these terms to learners for students to comprehend the lesson.

Apart from that, in this study the lack of availability of materials is seen and teachers suggest that in situations where materials are few, teachers might benefit from having access to a dictionary that lists vocabulary in Sinugboanong Binisaya together with definitions for common phrases used in their community. The phrases of Dabawenyon are not the same as the context of the materials provided, where Sinugboanong Binisaya is utilized in the textbooks. It is challenging for teachers to teach MTB-MLE to students as well as to themselves when they are unable to attend seminars. On top of that, no codified dialects and orthographies were provided in Davao Region which led to confusion of the teachers in Dawis Elementary School. The terminology used in Sinugboanong Binisaya, where the materials are based, differs greatly from what learners and teachers are used to.

Furthermore, the second objective of this study emerges themes which are lexical issues, a shortage of instructional materials, translation problems, and difficulties in comprehension that illustrates the recurrent challenges that arise while transitioning from utilizing the native language as the medium of instruction to adopting English as the instructional language. The issues mentioned earlier encompass lexical complexities about obstacles associated with vocabulary and terminology in an unfamiliar language. The educators and students faced challenges not only in terms of curriculum, instruction, and assessment but also encountered specific difficulties during the shift from Mother Tongue to English Language.

Along with the third objective of this study, it presents the various techniques to mitigate the obstacles encountered while implementing the MTB-MLE program. In addressing these challenges, teachers sought ways to minimize problems during the

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transition. They adopted strategies such as translating slowly, providing brief and concise explanations with concrete examples, incorporating objects, and using explicit teaching methods. Multilingual resources were also employed to offer various options to learners, fostering a more comfortable and enjoyable learning experience. The integration of technology, considered a powerful tool, played a crucial role in instruction. Teachers relied on pictures and videos, especially when dealing with children, to maintain students' attention and enhance understanding.

Correspondently, teachers emphasized the importance of encouraging students within the classroom. They urged learners to approach them with questions or confusion, creating an environment where making mistakes was seen as a natural part of the learning process. The teachers in Dawis Elementary School demonstrated patience and understanding, surpassing expectations despite the encountered challenges during the transition.

In summary, the difficulties faced by teachers in Dawis Elementary School did not determine them from fulfilling their role as second parents to their students. The educators' efforts, dedication, and hard work deserve recognition and applause, as they have gone above and beyond expectations in fostering a positive and effective learning environment.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The researchers would like to express their heartfelt gratitude to the following individuals who have contributed in the completion of this research work. To Dr. Tessie G. Miralles, for the continuous support and patience she extended as our adviser, for understanding and providing us immense knowledge. We would like to thank her for the valuable time and effort she shared that eventually motivated us to strive hard and overcome the difficulties we faced in our research endeavor; To their statistician Mrs. Joanna Reeve M. Canada, MAED for sharing knowledge and expertise in the analysis and interpretation of the data. To the panel of examiners who was chaired by Mr. Conrado B. Panerio, Mat-Math and his members for their constructive comments and suggestions for the improvement of the study; To Ms. Aloha Aguilar, for answering their queries, and sharing the templates and all the processes needed in the study; To the grades one to three teachers of Dawis Elementary School who answered the questions sincerely and with honesty; Above all, the researchers would like to express their deepest gratitude and sincere appreciation to Almighty God, the source of all things, for providing them with strength, knowledge, wisdom, and guidance throughout the course of this study, as they bring it to its final completion.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

There are no known conflicts of interest among the researchers working on this project. To guarantee the accuracy and impartiality of the research findings, we carried out the study and conducted an unbiased analysis of the data that was gathered. This impartiality shows that the researchers are free from any personal prejudices or conflicts of interest that might affect the study's findings or conclusions.

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